

INFLUENCE OF WATER ABSORPTION ON DELAMINATION INDUCED BY LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT AND CAI STRENGTH OF FRPS

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SUMMARY: An investigation of water absorption effects on the impact fracture mechanism and compression after impact (CAI) behavior was conducted using carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic matrix composite (AS-4/PEEK) and aramid fiber reinforced epoxy matrix composite (K-49/828), which have a quasi-isotropic stacking sequence of $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ]_{2S}$. The impact tests were carried out using a falling weight tester. Impact-induced internal damage was observed with a scanning acoustic microscope (SAM). The delamination area of AS-4/PEEK was much smaller than that of a CF/epoxy composite (MM-1/982X), and no influence of water absorption was observed. In contrast, that of K-49/828 was the largest, and the impact-load-induced delamination area was increased by water absorption. In the case of AS-4/PEEK, the compressive strength of the impacted specimen at 3J was the same as that of a virgin specimen, and no influence of water absorption was observed. Impact energy affected the CAI strength of K-49/828 as much as that of MM-1/982X. The fracture surface was closely examined using a scanning electron microscope, and the fracture mechanisms were discussed.

KEYWORDS: delamination, CF/PEEK composite, aramid fiber reinforced epoxy matrix composite, impact loading, compression after impact, water absorption, nondestructive inspection, scanning acoustic microscope

INTRODUCTION

Advanced fiber-reinforced polymer matrix composites (FRP) that have high strength and high stiffness-to-weight ratios are now widely used in high technology engineering applications. When these are used in a service condition, impact events, such as tool drops, occur, and environmental exposure also affects the mechanical properties of FRPs. Hence, influences of impact and environment on mechanical properties of FRPs must be clarified. It is well known that carbon/epoxy laminates are susceptible to low velocity impact [1,2]. To improve impact resistance, ductile matrix such as PEEK [3] and aramid fibers [4-6] are reported to be alternative candidate materials. In this study, effects of water absorption on impact fracture and compression after impact (CAI) behavior were investigated using carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic matrix composite (AS-4/PEEK) and aramid fiber (Kevlar 49) reinforced epoxy matrix composite (K-49/828), having a quasi-isotropic stacking sequence of $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ]_{2S}$. We compared the results with those of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy matrix composite (MM-1/982X) [1].

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The composites used in this study were carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic matrix (PEEK) composite (AS-4/PEEK) and aramid fiber (Kevlar 49) reinforced epoxy matrix composite (K-49/828), having a quasi-isotropic stacking sequence of $[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ]_{2S}$. Average thickness, fiber-volume fraction, tensile strength and initial elastic modulus are listed in Table 1. The data for MM-1/982X [1] is also listed. Rectangular specimens of 200mm in length and 40mm in width were used.

Specimens were immersed in distilled water at 80°C for 2 months. The weight gain of the specimens in time is shown in Fig.1, with the data of angle-ply AS-4/PEEK ($[45^\circ]_{3S}$) and unidirectionally reinforced AS-4/PEEK ($[0^\circ]_{14}$)[7]. In the case of AS-4/PEEK, the quasi-isotropic laminates absorbed more water than angle-ply and unidirectionally reinforced laminates. The angle-ply and the unidirectionally reinforced laminates were well fabricated, and no void was observed. However, the quasi-isotropic laminates contained many voids. Figure 2 shows the surface and the side surface of the quasi-isotropic laminate of AS-4/PEEK.

Table 1: Materials used in this study

Name	AS-4/PEEK	K-49/828	MM-1/982X
Construction of laminate	$[0^\circ/45^\circ/90^\circ]_{2S}$		
Average thickness mm	2.0	2.4	2.5
Fiber volume fraction %	61	66	59
Tensile strength MPa	720	500	840
Initial modulus GPa	48	31	63

Fig. 1: Relationship between weight gain and (immersional duration)^{1/2}

This is the reason why the quasi-isotropic laminate of AS-4/PEEK absorbed more water than other laminates ($[45^\circ]_{3S}$ and $[0^\circ]_{14}$). The weight gain of K-49/828 leveled off at 2.0%. The weight gain of MM-1/982X was about 1.0% [1]. Specimens immersed in water will be referred to as “wet” specimens, while the specimens held in room air referred to as “dry” specimens.

The impact tests were carried out by a falling weight tester. The steel ball (1/2 inch in diameter) was attached to the falling weight. By this steel ball, the center of specimen whose both ends (75mm) were fixed was impacted. Compression tests after impact (CAI) were performed on impacted dry and wet specimens, as well as non-impacted dry and wet specimens as a reference. Aluminum tabs were glued to both ends of a specimen, giving a gage length of 63mm. Compression tests were carried out at a constant crosshead speed of 1mm/min, using a electro-hydraulic servo controlled fatigue testing machine (Shimadzu, EHF-FB20, Load Capacity: 200kN).

The internal damage after impact was observed using a scanning acoustic microscope (SAM, Olympus Optical Co., UH3) with a pulse wave of 50MHz for 1600ns gate time. The fracture surfaces of the specimens were observed using a scanning electron microscope (SEM, JEOL, JSM-5400LV).

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Impact Test

Figures 3 and 4 respectively show the front and rear surfaces of impacted dry specimens of AS-4/PEEK and K-49/828. Front surface of AS-4/PEEK has a crease and rear surface has cracks. For K-49/828, there is no crease and crack. This means that the visible surface damage of K-49/828 is less than that of AS-4/PEEK.

Figures 5(a) and (b) show SAM photographs of a AS-4/PEEK specimen before and after impact test. In the case of AS-4/PEEK, even a virgin specimen had internal defects introduced by insufficient matrix infiltration. Therefore, the subtraction of SAM images between virgin and impacted specimens was adopted to evaluate impact-induced delamination. The result is shown in Fig. 5(c). We use the same method for K-49/828, which had no internal defect such as observed in AS-4/PEEK.

Fig.2: Virgin specimen (AS-4/PEEK)

Figure 6 shows the impact-induced delamination area as a function of impact energy. Delamination area of AS-4/PEEK was smaller than that of MM-1/982X, and no influence of water absorption was observed. For K-49/828, impact induced-delamination area was the largest, and it was increased by water absorption. The threshold impact energy below which no-delamination occurred was 3J for both dry and wet AS-4/PEEK specimens. For K-49/828, it was assumed to be almost 0J.

On the fracture surfaces of an impacted AS-4/PEEK specimen, many defects introduced during manufacturing could be observed (Fig.7). Those defects were imaged by SAM as white areas, shown in Figure 5(a). Figure 8 shows a cross section of an impacted point. A crack is initiated at a defect. Improved manufacturing process will further increase the impact resistance of the composite.

Fig. 3: Impacted specimen (AS-4/PEEK)

The characteristic fracture feature of AS-4/PEEK is that the fiber surface was covered by matrix material, irrespective of water absorption (Fig.9). This indicates that the composite had superior fiber/matrix interfacial strength. There is little difference in fracture morphology between dry and wet specimen. For K-49/828, the fracture was caused by interfacial debonding (Fig.10), indicating low fiber/matrix interfacial strength of the composite. Figure 11 shows the magnified fiber surface in K-49/828. Although water absorption was reported to promote fiber splitting [8-10], the number of fiber splitting of the wet specimens were less than that of dry ones. This means that water absorption degraded the fiber/matrix interfacial strength, thereby promoting the impact-induced delamination by water absorption.

Fig. 4: Impacted specimens (K-49/828)

Fig. 5 (a): SAM photograph of virgin specimen (AS-4/PEEK)

Fig. 5 (b): SAM photograph of impacted specimen (AS-4/PEEK)

Fig. 5 (c): Extracted delamination (AS-4/PEEK)

Fig. 6: Relationship between impact energy and delamination area

Fig. 7: Fracture surface (AS-4/PEEK, Dry specimen, Impact energy: 5J)

Fig. 8 Cross section of an impacted point (AS-4/PEEK), Dry specimen, Impact energy: 5J)

(a) Dry specimen

(b) Wet specimen

Fig. 9 Fracture surface of AS-4/PEEK (Impact energy: 5J)

CAI Test

The relationship between impact energy and residual compressive strength after impact is illustrated in Fig. 12. In the case of AS-4/PEEK, the compressive strength of the impacted

specimen at 3J was the same as that of a virgin specimen, because no impact-induced delamination occurred. Above 3J, however, residual compressive strength decreased with an increase in impact energy. Also we must note that no influence of water absorption was observed. The compressive strength of K-49/828 was the lowest in all FRPs tested, as the aramid fiber has low compressive strength [11].

To examine the ratio of the residual compressive strength to the compressive strength of non-impacted specimens, the relationship between impact energy and normalized residual compressive strength was analyzed (Fig.13). The normalized strength was defined by residual compressive strength divided by compressive strength of non-impacted specimen in a respective environment. The normalized strength of AS-4/PEEK was the highest, indicating superior resistance against impact. For K-49/828, it was almost the same as that of MM-1/982X.

Fig. 10: Fracture surface of K-49/828
(Impact energy: 5J)

Fig.11: Magnified fiber surface
(K-49/828, Impact energy:5J)

The relationship between impact-induced delamination area and normalized residual compressive strength is illustrated in Fig. 14. At a certain delamination area, the normalized residual compressive strength of K-49/828 was higher than that of MM-1/982X. However, impact-induced delamination area of K-49/828 was larger than that of MM-1/982X (Fig.6).

Therefore, as is shown in Fig. 13, the normalized residual compressive strength of K-49/828 and MM-1/982X was similar when compared at a certain impact energy.

Fig. 12 Relationship between impact energy and residual compressive strength

Fig. 13 Relationship between impact energy and normalized residual compressive strength

CONCLUSIONS

1. Even though composites have initial defects introduced by a defective manufacturing process, the delamination area can be accurately evaluated by the subtraction of SAM images between virgin and impacted specimens.
2. The surface damage tolerance of K-49/828 is superior to that of AS-4/PEEK.
3. Delamination area of AS-4/PEEK was the smallest, and no influence of water absorption was observed. For K-49/828, impact induced-delamination was the largest, and it was increased by water absorption. The impact-induced delamination tolerance of PEEK matrix composite is superior to that of epoxy matrix composite.
4. The compressive strength of K-49/828 was the lowest in all FRPs tested. However, the normalized residual compressive strength of K-49/828 was the same as that of MM-1/982X. In the case of AS-4/PEEK, the normalized CAI strength was the highest, indicating superior resistance against impact. Also there is no influence of water absorption in AS-4/PEEK, showing superior resistance against water absorption.
5. At a certain delamination area, the normalized residual compressive strength of K-49/828 was higher than that of MM-1/982X. However, the delamination area of K-49/828 was larger than that of MM-1/982X. Therefore, the normalized residual compressive strength of K-49/828 became almost the same as that of MM-1/982X, when compared at a certain impact energy.
6. The fracture surface examined indicates that AS-4/PEEK has superior fiber/matrix interfacial strength. However, K-49/828 has low fiber/matrix interfacial strength. In the case of K-49/828, the number of fiber splitting of the wet specimens were less than that of dry ones, because water absorption degraded the fiber/matrix interfacial strength.

Fig.14 Relationship between delamination area and normalized residual compressive strength

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